

This resource is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

You may:

- ✓ Share — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format
- ✓ Adapt — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially

Under the following terms:

- ✓ Attribution — You must give appropriate credit to:
Susan Ardila, M.Ed., MindBridge Math Mastery
<https://www.mindbridgemath.com>

- ✓ Include a link to the license:
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

- ✓ Indicate if changes were made.

No additional restrictions may be applied.